

Value of Acute-Phase Proteins in the PNL Surgery and Complications

Running Title: *Acute Phase Protein Levels in PNL Surgery*

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ABSTRACT

Background: Percutaneous nephrolithotomy is currently recommended as the first-line treatment of large kidney stones ≥ 20 mm. Success rates in the treatment of simple kidney stones with percutaneous nephrolithotomy are reported to be quite high with low morbidity.

Aim: In this study we tried to elucidate the preoperative and postoperative haematological, biochemical and acute phase protein changes in patients who underwent percutaneous nephrolithotomy and percutaneous nephrolithotomy surgery complications.

Materials & Method: A total of 85 patients who have been operated via PNL due to kidney stones in our institution between 2019 and 2021 and patients who underwent ESWL as a control group were included in this study. Hemogram, blood biochemistry, C-Reactive Protein, Haptoglobin, transferrin values were analyzed in all patients before and at 1,3 and 30 days after surgery. The acute phase protein changes in case of complications in 35 patients who developed complications in PNL surgery were analyzed.

Results: The ROC analysis evaluation revealed that CRP value of 82.2 and HPT value of over 5.79 and a TRF value of less than 2.11 may lead to the development of complications.

Conclusion: According to the results of this study one can conclude that acute phase proteins are easy to obtain, cost – effective and predictive in patients undergoing PNL complications in comparison to ESWL.

Keywords: *Percutaneous nephrolithotomy, complication, Extracorporeal Shock Wave Lithotripsy, CRP, HPT, transferrin*

Abbreviations:

APP: *acute phase proteins*

ASA: *American Society of Anesthesiologists physical status classification system*

BUN: *blood urea nitrogen*

CI: *confidence interval*

CRP: *C Reactive protein*

CT: *computerized tomography*

EAU: *European Association of Urology*

ESWL: *Extracorporeal Shock Wave Lithotripsy*

HPT: *haptoglobin*

ICU: *Intensive Care Unit*

KUB films: *kidney, ureter, bladder films*

OR: *odds ratio*

PNL: *Percutaneous nephrolithotomy*

RIRC: *retrograde intrarenal surgery*

ROC: *Receiver Operating Characteristics*

SD: *standard deviation*

SIRS: *Systemic inflammatory response syndrome*

SPSS: *Statistical Package for the Social Sciences*

TRF: *transferrin*

UTI: *urinary tract infections*

Introduction

The prevalence of kidney stones in Turkey is thought to be endemic reaching up to 11.1% of urologic admission (1). There are different techniques to be performed such as percutaneous nephrolithotomy (PNL), extracorporeal shock wave lithotripsy (ESWL), retrograde intrarenal surgery (RIRC), laparoscopy and open surgery (1, 2). Percutaneous nephrolithotomy (PNL) is currently recommended as the first-line treatment of large kidney stones ≥ 20 mm. Percutaneous nephrolithotomy (PNL), briefly, enters through a small hole created between the skin and the kidney to remove the stones and can be described as a cure. PNL is the preferred treatment method in kidney stones over 2 cm, multiple kidney stones and staghorn kidney stones (1). Success rates in the treatment of simple kidney stones with PNL are reported to be quite high with low morbidity, short hospital stay and less workload when appropriate equipment is used (3). Additionally, PNL causes less morbidity than open surgery, upper urinary system percutaneous surgery and standard techniques. The rate of complications has been dramatically reduced with the introduction of percutaneous surgery, a minimally invasive procedure (4). However, an urologist should always be aware that there may be significant complications during and after the PNL procedure. Among the most common complications encountered are fever, bleeding, problems due to urine leakage and residual stones (5).

The procedure success after PNL varies between 40% to 90% and depends on various factors such as number of stones, location, chemical structure, and surgeon's experience. The main reason for not achieving complete stone-free status during PNL can be elaborated as stone or stone fragments escaping into an inaccessible calyx, bleeding, and prolonged termination of the time-dependent operation (7). However, the wrong choice of surgical technique, anatomical abnormalities, stone composition, and technical difficulties can affect

the number and size of residual stones. Residual stone fragments cause pain, urinary infection, stone growth, obstruction, and secondary surgery imposes various risks (8).

Although perioperative fever and sterile urine are detected preoperatively; fever may occur even with the use of prophylactic antibiotics, because in several cases the stone itself can be a source of infection (9). Intraoperative stone culture may be useful in determining the antibiotic to be used after surgery (10, 11). Keeping the irrigation pressure below 30mmHg during PNL and ensuring postoperative urinary drainage may prevent the development of septic complications (12). The most frequent complications of PNL can be elaborated as fever, urinary tract infection, and sepsis. These can prolong hospitalisation, duration of intensive care unit stay and require additional antibiotic treatment. SIRS (*systemic inflammatory response syndrome*) may be observed in patients with severe infections (13, 14). Given the poor predictive value of preoperative voiding culture, acute phase reactants are positioned as the first choice of biomarkers as they are easy to obtain and cost-effective (13).

Preoperative and postoperative acute phase proteins are both inexpensive and noninvasive measure CRP is the major determinant of these inflammatory markers. CRP, a protein synthesized from the liver in inflammatory reactions, is used for the recognition and elimination of pathogens, clearance of necrotic and apoptotic cells. It is synthesized in the body within 4 – 6 hours and doubles within 8 hours. It takes about 1 week to return to normal values in the blood following the inflammatory processes. It can increase 15-40 times in invasive bacterial infections, 3-5 times in viral infections, and more than 10 times in influenza or CMV infections (14). Ferritin is stimulated by infection and infectious situation could mislead higher iron storage than it truly exists in case referring to the concentration of plasma ferritin. Ferritin can increase 1000 times rapidly due to its short half-life, while transferrin levels decrease depending on the severity. Regarding this, ferritin can be measured to determine response to infectious and non-infectious inflammation and monitor to evaluate the success of treatment interventions (15, 16). Haptoglobin, a protein which transports hemoglobin, becomes elevated during an acute-phase reaction and decrease in hemolytic conditions and severe hepatocellular deficiency (14).

Study Hypothesis

In this study we tried to elucidate the preoperative and postoperative haematological, biochemical, and acute phase protein changes in patients who underwent percutaneous nephrolithotomy surgery due to kidney stones and compared them with patients who underwent ESWL treatment. This study has also aimed to determine the change of APP proteins and threshold values in patients with developing complications.

Materials & Method

A total of 85 patients who have been operated via PNL due to kidney stones in our institution between 2019 and 2021 and patients who underwent ESWL as a control group were included in this study. The ethics committee approval has been granted at 01.04.2021 and protocol number: 2021/36. Informed consent has been obtained from all participants.

Inclusion Criteria

Individuals who were aged between 18 to 60 years and ASA classes I and II have been enrolled in the analysis.

Exclusion Criteria

Patients with liver dysfunction and abnormal blood coagulation were not included in the study. Patients with a history of cancer and/or immune diseases were also excluded. Subjects who had positive culture before the surgery has been treated and included in the study after negative culture result.

Hemogram, blood biochemistry, C-Reactive Protein, Haptoglobin, transferrin values were analyzed in all patients before and at 1,3 and 30 days after surgery. We tried to determine the factors affecting the complication and the threshold value of acute phase protein change in case of complications in 35 patients who developed complications in PNL surgery.

All of the surgeries were performed by the same surgeon and adhered to the standard technique. A 6F open-ended ureteral stent is placed by means of a rigid cystoscope. With the patient positioned prone, percutaneous renal access is obtained through the appropriate calix by the urologists using fluoroscopic assistance. Percutaneous tracts were located at the 11th intercostal space or the 12th subcostal site under skopi guidance with an 18-gauge needle. Serial dilation of the tracts was performed with a fascial dilator up to 30 Fr. Stones were fragmented with a pnomotik lithotripter. Large fragments were extracted by a grasper, and fragments smaller than 3mm were primarily pushed out. The surgeries were considered complete when residual fragments were not detected under an endoscope and skopi. A 20 F foley tube were placed in an antegrade setting. Operation time was measured from insertion of the ureteral catheter until the placement of the nephrostomy tube after completion of the procedure. After PNL, patients received a 3-day dose of intravenous antibiotic treatment. Following stone removal, a plain abdominal radiograph and a nephrostogram were obtained within 48 hours in order to verify that the stone has been completely removed and the collecting system has remained intact.

ESWL was performed as an outpatient procedure using an electrohydraulic extracorporeal lithotripter. Intra-muscular non-steroidal anti-inflammatory medication was administered prior to the procedure, and The procedure was concluded after seeing fragmentation on fluoroscopy or after a maximum of 3,000 shock waves. Patients without clearance after three sessions were referred for other modalities or follow-up. Additional sessions were not scheduled earlier than 15 days. ESWL patients were followed after the first session. The second session has been performed after follow up period of first month.

Postoperative complications were stratified according to the modified Clavien classification system. Vital signs were closely monitored, and abdominal plain film examinations were rescheduled the next morning. Culture-specific antibiotics treatment and antibiotic treatment continued until PNL. A stone-free status was regarded as nodetectable stones on KUB films 1 month after PNL. Additionally, NCCT would likely be required if KUB showed any signs of high density. Fragments less than 4mm were also considered as not meaningful stones when determining stone clearance.

Modified Clavien Classification System (17)

Grade I: Any deviation from the normal postoperative course without the need for pharmacological treatment or surgical, endoscopic, and radiological interventions. Allowed therapeutic regimens are: antiemetics, antipyretics, analgesics, diuretics, electrolytes, and physiotherapy.

Grade II: Requiring pharmacological treatment with drugs other than such allowed for grade I complications.

Grade IIIa: Requiring surgical, endoscopic, or radiological interventions not under general anaesthesia.

Grade IIIb: Requiring surgical, endoscopic, or radiological interventions under general anaesthesia.

Grade IVa: Life-threatening complication requiring ICU management (single organ dysfunction).

Grade IVb: Life-threatening complication requiring ICU management (multiple organ dysfunction).

Grade V: Death

Statistical Analysis

Data analysis was performed in SPSS for Windows 23.0 package program. Frequency and percentage were given for categorical data, and median, minimum and maximum descriptive values for continuous data. Categorical variables were evaluated with the Chi-square test. Evaluation of the difference between groups was done with the Kruskal Wallis Test. The effects of risk factors, which were thought to have a significant effect on the development of complications as a result of univariate statistical analyzes, were investigated with Logistic Regression analysis. Odds Ratio, 95% confidence interval for each risk factor was calculated. Calculation of breakpoints for complication development was evaluated by ROC analysis. The results were considered statistically significant when the p value was less than 0.05.

Results

A total of 145 patients has been enrolled in this study. Individuals who had percutaneous nephrolithotomy surgery were divided into two groups as those with and without complications and were compared with the control (ESWL) group. Sixty subjects were included in the ESWL group but 10 of them had been discontinued due to elevated CRP levels. Demographic and laboratory evaluation results of these three groups were given in *Table 1*. The median age of the PNL group ($n=50$) was 43 years (*ranging between 22 – 72 years*), PNL complication group ($n=35$) was 48 years (*ranging between 22 – 72 years*) and ESWL group ($n=50$) was 45 years (*ranging between 15 – 80 years*). The gender ratio was numerically in favor of males 63% ($n=85$) compared to women 37% ($n=50$). The side of the procedure was right side in 39% ($n=53$) and left side in 61% ($n=82$) of the individuals. However, it should be mentioned that no statistical difference has existed between the groups in terms of age, gender, and operation side (*Table 1*).

The localization of the stone was mostly detected at the renal pelvis in 66% ($n=33$) of the PNL group, 54.3% ($n=19$) of PNL complication group and 30% ($n=15$) of ESWL group with no significance. No stone has been detected at upper kidney pole in PNL group, 5.7% ($n=2$) in the PNL complication group and 6% ($n=3$) in the ESWL group ($p<0.0001$).

Table 1 indicates various statistically significant parameters among 3 patient groups. The size of the stone ($p<0,0001$), Hg before the operation and on the first day ($p<0,0001$), the number of white blood cells on the first and third days ($p<0,0001$), BUN on the first ($p<0.001$) and third day ($p<0.016$), creatinine level at the first day ($p<0,002$), CRP in the first ($p<0,0001$) and third ($p<0,0001$) day, HPT on the first ($p<0,0001$), third ($p<0,0001$) day and first month ($p<0,0001$) and TRF parameters before the operation ($p<0,001$), on the first ($p<0,0001$) and third ($p<0,0001$) days.

As a result of the post-hoc analysis to determine which group caused the difference in the parameters that were statistically significant between the three groups, it was seen that the difference was mostly due to the evaluation results of the individuals in the control group

(ESWL). When the table was examined, the results of the individuals in the control group were generally lower than the evaluation results of the PNL group thus, causing a statistical difference.

The evaluation of results affecting the development of complications in individuals who had Percutaneous Nephrolithotomy (PNL) surgery were given in Table 2. When the table was examined, the development of complications were due to Mai mik ($p < 0,0001$), first day Hg ($p < 0,001$), number of white blood cells on the first ($p < 0,001$) and third ($p < 0,001$) day and first month ($p < 0,015$), BUN on the first ($p < 0,003$) and third ($p < 0,028$) day, creatinine on the first day ($p < 0,027$), CRP in the first ($p < 0,012$) and third ($p < 0,0001$) day, HPT in the first ($p < 0,0001$) and third ($p < 0,0001$) day, and TRF parameters before the operation ($p < 0,001$), on the first ($p < 0,0001$) and third ($p < 0,0001$) days.

Some of these parameters, had reduced the development of complications have been elaborated for the study groups (PNL+complications and PNL) respectively as follows: on the first day, the Hg increase was 1/1.6, approximately 0.6 times, increase in TRF on the first day was 1/11.4, approximately 0.1 times, and the increase in TRF on the third day by 1/3.2 and approximately 0.3 times.

On the other hand, significant parameters had an increasing effect on the development of complications. It has been determined that a one-unit increase in the Mai mic value increases the complication development 1/0.7, approximately 1.4 times increase in white blood cell increase days increased the development of complications 1/0.9, that is, 1.1 times in both times. One-unit increase in creatinine value on the first day increased the development of complications 1/0.3 and approximately 3.3 times, increases in CRP values on the first and third days, respectively, increased the development of complications by 1/0.9 (1.1 times) and 1/0.96 (ie 1.04 times). Increases in the first and third day HPT values increased the development of complications 1/0.05, ie 20 times, and 1/0.2, ie 5 times, respectively. It was determined that a one-unit decrease in the TRF value before the operation increased the complication development by 1/0.15 and approximately 6.7 times.

As a result of the ROC (*Receiver Operating Characteristics*) analysis evaluation, it was observed that a CRP value of 82.2 and a HPT value of over 5.79 and a TRF value of less than 2.11 may lead to the development of complications.

The most common bacteria in urine were *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Escherichia coli*, both 20%. This study had a total complication rate of 16%, approximately 10% which were severe. The most common complication of PCNL was infection (60%), followed by bleeding (5.4%), re-operation (1.6%) and pain (0.5%).

Discussion

Acute-phase reactants can be elaborated as a group of liver originated proteins that has been synthesized in response to several inflammatory and infectious situations. Their secretion can be induced via cytokines, growth factors, anaphylatoxins, glucocorticoids and catecholamines. The response of these acute phase proteins can be both increase and decrease of plasma levels. Reduced albumin and transferrin levels are observed while CRP, haptoglobin, fibrinogen and others increase. The role of these mediators can be explained as ameliorating tissue damage, regeneration and neutralizing inflammation.

Urine culture, an old school indicator has been used for a long time to predict postoperative fever after PNL (18). However, Gutierrez et al. (20) have shown that 8.8% of PNL performed subjects with with negative preoperative urine cultures cultivated 18.2% positive cultures in the postoperative period (16). Mariappan et al. (20) has gone one step further and reported that positive stone culture and pelvic urine are better predictors of potential urosepsis than bladder urine (18). Although perioperative fever and sterile urine are detected preoperatively; fever may occur even with the use of prophylactic antibiotics, because in several cases the stone itself can be a source of infection (9). Intraoperative stone culture may be useful in determining the antibiotic to be used after surgery (10, 11).

CRP is often perceived as a non-specific acute phase reactant as it is elevated in diseases like rheumatoid arthritis, cardiovascular disease, vascular diseases and sometimes

may not be elevated in several inflammatory diseases such as scleroderma, ulcerative colitis and SLE. Additionally, CRP levels are strongly associated with the patient's age and immunological status. In this study we have found statistically significant CRP increase in the first and third day of pre-operative period and first and third day of postoperative period.

In case of infection and/or inflammation, haptoglobin, increases simultaneously and forms a complex with hemoglobin as a positive acute phase reactant. It also decreases in hemolytic conditions and severe hepatocellular deficiency. In this study we found a significant increase in HPT in the first, third day and 30th day. Also the HPT levels significantly increased in the first and third day of postoperative period. Increases in the first and third day HPT values also increased the development of complications 1/0.05, ie 20 times, and 1/0.2, ie 5 times, respectively.

Ferritin is also another acute phase reactant and it is elevated in inflammation with other mediators like CRP and ESR. During inflammation and/or infection iron is not released to transferrin (*TRF*) and transferrin-bound iron, is low despite a normal or elevated ferritin. In this study we found decreased TRF levels before the operation, on the first and third days. One-unit increase in the TRF value before the operation increased the complication development by 1/0.15 and approximately 6.7 times.

Regarding all the data above ROC analysis evaluation revealed that a CRP value of 82.2 and a HPT value of over 5.79 and a TRF value of less than 2.11 may be observed in case of complications.

The most common complication of PNL can be stated as postoperative fever 39.8% and it is usually transient in nature (18). Only 9.3% patients develop sepsis as further case (19). One other complication is UTIs which may originate from surgical manipulation and/or fragmentation of calculi or the introduction of bacteria via the nephrostomy tract (20). The surgeon should consider antibiotic treatment before PNL procedure and even continue for postoperative 4 days following stone removal according to European Association of Urology (EAU) guidelines (21). On the contrary, one should bear in mind that antibiotic utilisation does not eliminate all the infection risks alone. Sharifi et al. (2006) reported that 16.2% of

patients had positive bladder urine culture in the preoperative period (21) and this has ratio has ranged between 4.1% to 53.6% (19). The complication rate of our study has been 16%, approximately 10% which were severe. The most common complication of PCNL was infection (60%), followed by bleeding (5.4%), re-operation (1.6%) and pain (0.5%).

Gutierrez et al. (2012) published that E. coli was the most commonly isolated microorganism, accounting for 40.5% of positive cultures in their study (22). Previous studies have also emphasized E. Coli as the dominant bacteria (up to 60%) in UTIs (23). In this study, the most common bacteria in urine were Enterococcus faecalis and Escherichia coli, both 20%.

Limitations of the Study

The main limitation of the study could be attributed to its relatively low population size and the low number of complications.

The strengths of this study can be elaborated in two major points. First, all the patients had undergone abdominal CT in prone position before percutaneous nephrolithotomy surgery in order to detect the localization of the stone accurately. The neighborhood of the kidney and the colon has been re-evaluated to eliminate the risk of colon perforation due to surgery. Secondly, although there were many studies on the complications of percutaneous nephrolithotomy surgery, most of them depends on the radiologic data. However, our study has been conducted on a simple blood test. Acute phase proteins have been routinely utilized in many specializations but never investigated for percutaneous nephrolithotomy surgery. The control group of this study consisted of ESWL patients indicating that the stone elimination has been considered efficiently.

Conclusion

According to the results of this study one can conclude that acute phase proteins are easy to obtain, cost – effective and predictive in patients undergoing PNL in comparison to ESWL.

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Tables

Table – 1: *Analysis of Demographic and Laboratory Parameters by Groups*

Table – 2: *Analysis of Factors Affecting the Development of PNL AFP Complications*

Table – 3: *ROC analysis for CRP, HPT and TRF on Day One Postoperative for Complication Development*

Table – 4: *Complications following PNL operation*

Table 1: *Analysis of Demographic and Laboratory Parameters by Groups*

Characteristics (N=135)	PNL AFP Complications (n=35)	PNL AFP (n=50)	ESWL AFP(n=50)	p	Difference*
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	Median (Min- Max) n (%)	Median (Min- Max) n (%)	Median (Min- Max) n (%)		
Age, years	48 (18-79)	43 (22-72)	45 (15-80)	0.451	
Gender					
Male	26 (74.3)	33 (66.0)	26 (52.0)	0.095	
Female	9 (25.7)	17 (34.0)	24 (48.0)		
Area					
Right Side	13 (37.1)	18 (36.0)	22 (44.0)	0.684	
Left Side	22 (62.9)	32 (64.0)	28 (56.0)		
Stone localisation					
Kidney Upper Pole	2 (5.7)	-	3 (6.0)	<0.0001	
Kidney Median Pole	5 (14.3)	9 (18.0)	18 (36.0)		
Renal Pelvis	19 (54.3)	33 (66.0)	15 (30.0)		
Kidney Lower Pole	8 (22.9)	8 (16.0)	2 (4.0)		
Uretra Upper End	1 (2.9)	-	8 (16.0)		
Uretra Median Zone	-	-	4 (8.0)		
Stone size (mm²)	658.4 (345.6-1983)	730 (324.8-1880.4)	130.6 (39.8-1178.5)	<0.0001	a-c/b-c
Pre-op Hg	13.3 (11.2-17.2)	13.6 (10.8-17.8)	11.7 (9.8-16.8)	<0.0001	a-c/b-c
P1 Hg	10.4 (6.6-15.9)	11.5 (9.9-17.3)	11.5 (9.9-17.3)	0.001	a-b/a-c
P30 Hg	12.8 (1.5-16.8)	13.1 (10.8-17.4)	12.7 (10.2-17.4)	0.213	
Pre-op Bk	8.1 (5.5-10.4)	8.2 (5.2-12.2)	8.4 (5.2-10.4)	0.970	
P1 Bk	18.3 (12.8-38.9)	14.9 (7.2-24.2)	7.5 (5.5-11.2)	<0.0001	a-b-c
P30 Bk	8.3 (6.4-12.9)	7.5 (5.5-11.5)	8.0 (5.2-10.4)	0.065	
Pre-op BUN	15 (8-25)	15 (6-24)	16 (7-35)	0.441	
P1 BUN	20 (11-82)	15 (7-40)	16 (10-30)	0.001	a-b/a-c
P30 BUN	16 (8-27)	15 (7-27)	14.5 (8-27)	0.370	
Pre-Op Cr	0.8 (0.4-9.0)	0.8 (0.1-9.0)	0.8 (0.4-9.0)	0.743	
P1 Cr	1.0 (0.6-3.4)	0.9 (0.6-1.7)	0.8 (0.5-1.7)	0.002	a-b/a-c
P30 Cr	0.8 (0.5-1.1)	0.8 (0.4-1.7)	0.8 (0.4-1.5)	0.458	
Pre-op CRP	3.1 (3.1-3.1)	3.1 (3.1-3.1)	3.1 (3.1-3.1)	1.000	
P1 CRP	252.4 (74.3-595.7)	72.9 (26.8-91.3)	5.7 (3.1-9.9)	<0.0001	a-b-c
P30 CRP	3.1 (3.1-3.1)	3.1 (3.1-3.1)	3.1 (3.1-3.1)	1.000	
Pre-Op HPT	1.43 (0.34-2.63)	1.61 (0.82-5.38)	1.33 (0.62-1.86)	0.066	
P1 HPT	7.15 (5.25-9.94)	4.56 (3.24-6.95)	1.36 (0.23-1.86)	<0.0001	a-b-c
P30 HPT	1.73 (0.31-12.2)	1.66 (0.51-2.83)	1.37 (0.29-1.85)	<0.0001	a-c/b-c
Pre-op TRF	3.02 (2.04-3.96)	2.51 (1.91-3.24)	2.56 (2.02-3.68)	0.001	a-b/a-c
P1 TRF	1.29 (0.27-2.94)	2.41 (1.91-3.11)	2.32 (1.98-3.16)	<0.0001	a-c/b-c

P30 TRF

2.39 (1.22-3.11)

2.55 (1.24-3.68)

2.57 (1.96-3.68)

0.178

* $a = \text{PNL AFP Complications}$, $b = \text{PNL AFP}$, $c = \text{ESWL}$

Table 2: *Analysis of Factors Affecting the Development of PNL AFP Complications*

Characteristics (N=85)	PNL AFP		P Value	OR (95% CI)
	Complications (n=35)	PNL AFP (n=50)		
	Median (Min-Max) n (%)	Median (Min-Max) n (%)		
Age, years	48 (18-79)	43 (22-72)	0.358	0.986 (0.956-1.016)
Gender				
Male	26 (74.3)	33 (66.0)	-	1.000 ^a
Female	9 (25.7)	17 (34.0)	0.416	1.488 (0.571-3.877)
Area				
Right Side	13 (37.1)	18 (36.0)	-	1.000 ^a
Left Side	22 (62.9)	32 (64.0)	0.914	1.051 (0.429-2.575)
Ans Period	160 (60 – 280)	150 (70-365)	0.476	0.997 (0.990-1.005)
Operation Time, minutes	145 (45 – 260)	122 (45-245)	0.304	0.996 (0.988-1.004)
Residual Stones	11 (31.4)	8 (16.0)	0.098	0.416 (0.147-1.175)
Mai Mik	22 (12 – 28)	15 (6-24)	<0.0001	0.783 (0.699-0.877)
Stone size (mm ²)	658.4 (345.6 – 1983)	730 (324.8-1880.4)	0.888	1.000 (0.999-1.001)
Pre-op Hg	13.3 (11.2 – 17.2)	13.6 (10.8-17.8)	0.182	1.210 (0.915-1.600)
P1 Hg	10,4 (6.6 – 15.9)	11.5 (9.9-17.3)	0.001	1.592 (1.211-2.093)
P3 Hg	11.6 (9.8 – 15.8)	11.6 (9.9-17.0)	0.324	1.177 (0.851-1.628)
P30 Hg	12.8 (1.5-16.8)	13.1 (10.8-17.4)	0.131	1.217 (0.943-1.571)
Pre-op Bk	8.1 (5.5-10.4)	8.2 (5.2-12.2)	0.987	0.998 (0.742-1.341)
P1 Bk	18.3 (12.8-38.9)	14.9 (7.2-24.2)	<0.0001	0.644 (0.521-0.796)
P3 Bk	15.4 (5.2-25.7)	10.0 (5.8-14.1)	<0.0001	0.738 (0.636-0.857)
P30 Bk	8.3 (6.4-12.9)	7.5 (5.5-11.5)	0.015	0.701 (0.527-0.932)
Pre-op BUN	15 (8-25)	15 (6-24)	0.480	0.964 (0.871-1.067)
P1 BUN	20 (11-82)	15 (7-40)	0.003	0.914 (0.860-0.971)
P3 BUN	15 (7-64)	12 (7-43)	0.028	0.938 (0.886-0.993)
P30 BUN	16 (8-27)	15 (7-27)	0.350	0.955 (0.867-1.052)
Pre-Op Cr	0.8 (0.4-9.0)	0.8 (0.1-9.0)	0.734	0.943 (0.673-1.322)
P1 Cr	1.0 (0.6-3.4)	0.9 (0.6-1.7)	0.027	0.313 (0.112-0.874)
P3 Cr	0.8 (0.6-2.6)	0.9 (0.6-1.5)	0.304	0.478 (0.117-1.953)
P30 Cr	0.8 (0.5-1.1)	0.8 (0.4-1.7)	0.248	3.749 (0.399-35.217)
Pre-op CRP	3.1 (3.1-3.1)	3.1 (3.1-3.1)	NA	NA
P1 CRP	252.4 (74.3-595.7)	72.9 (26.8-91.3)	0.012	0.898 (0.826-0.977)
P3 CRP	152.4 (22.5-387.5)	36.7 (10.6-66.2)	<0.0001	0.952 (0.929-0.976)

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P30 CRP	3.1 (3.1-3.1)	3.1 (3.1-3.1)	NA	NA
Pre-Op HPT	1.43 (0.34-2.63)	1.61 (0.82-5.38)	0.072	2.045 (0.939-4.451)
P1 HPT	7.15 (5.25-9.94)	4.56 (3.24-6.95)	<0.0001	0.049 (0.012-0.206)
P3 HPT	3.93 (2.37-7.95)	3.13 (2.13-4.89)	<0.0001	0.178 (0.076-0.420)
P30 HPT	1.73 (0.31-12.2)	1.66 (0.51-2.83)	0.063	0.625 (0.381-1.025)
Pre-op TRF	3.02 (2.04-3.96)	2.51 (1.91-3.24)	<0.0001	0.153 (0.054-0.433)
P1 TRF	1.29 (0.27-2.94)	2.41 (1.91-3.11)	<0.0001	11.402 (1.176-110.5)
P3 TRF	1.94 (0.80-2.95)	2.22 (1.91-2.99)	<0.0001	3.135 (1.052-5.653)
P30 TRF	2.39 (1.22-3.11)	2.55 (1.24-3.68)	0.074	2.472 (0.917-6.665)

OR: Odds Ratio, CI: Confidence Interval, a: Reference Category

Table 3: ROC analysis for CRP, HPT and TRF on Day One Postoperative for Complication Development

Risk Factors	AUC (95% CI)	Cut-off	P	Sensitivity (%)	Specifity (%)
CRP	0.944 (0.897 – 0.991)	82.2	<0.0001	91.4	76.0
HPT	0.969 (0.937 – 1.000)	5.79	<0.0001	97.1	88.0
TRF	0.923 (0.858 – 0.988)	2.11	<0.0001	88.6	76.0

Table – 4: *Complications following PNL operation*

	Modified Clavien Classification	N (%)
1.Post-op Fever	Grade 1	11 (22.4)
2.Post-op UTI	Grade 1	6 (12.2)
2.1.Post-op urine culture reproduction	Grade 1	5 (10.2)
3.DJ Stent insertion	Grade 2	10 (20.4)
3.1.Due to leakage after nephrostomy	Grade 2	5 (10.2)
3.2. URS due to ureteral stone	Grade 3A	4 (8.2)
3.3. Clot colic	Grade 3A	1 (2.0)
4. No blood transfusion	Grade 2	11 (22.4)
5.Sepsis and blood transfusion	Grade 2	1 (2.0)
6.Blood transfusion for bleeding and treatment after nephrostomy	Grade 2	2 (4.1)
7.Post-op blood transfusion due to decrease in hemoglobin	Grade 2	4 (8.2)
8. Chest tube insertion and blood transfusion due to post-op Left Hemotrochas	Grade 3A	1 (2.0)
9.Post-op Bronchospasm and blood transfusion	Grade 2	1 (2.0)
10.Post-op Resistant hypotension and blood transfusion	Grade 2	1 (2.0)
11.Post-op Atrial fibrillation and blood transfusion	Grade 2	1 (2.0)
TOTAL		49 (100.0)